

Balancing Photorealism and Transparency: A FAIR Approach to 3D Digitisation for Cultural Heritage documentation and dissemination

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Introduction

In recent years, the application of 3D technologies to cultural heritage dissemination has deepened the intertwining between GLAM and the gaming industry. The pipelines borrowed from 3D authoring in gaming greatly enhance the potential for photorealism in Web3D rendering technologies. However, this comes at the cost of the scientific accuracy of 3D reconstructions, as these technologies require significant simplification of both geometry and textures. Furthermore, despite the growing use of 3D technologies in archaeology and museums to study, disseminate, and enhance cultural heritage, the lack of a standardised and shared methodology raises issues of accessibility, transparency, and interoperability in the research domain, especially concerning the 3D data manipulation and authorial intervention performed to fix gaps due to acquisition conditions (ICOMOS General Assembly 2017).

Building on these premises, this article aims to address two complementary research questions: **RQ1:** Is it possible to achieve an acceptable level of photorealism for the GLAM sector for Web3D applications using a FAIR approach?

RQ2: In the context of such a workflow, where dissemination potential and scientific value should be simultaneously pursued, how can transparency related to the reliability and authenticity of the data be improved?

This contribution introduces a defined pipeline designed to deliver photorealistic results while adhering to FAIR principles, emphasising reusability, sustainability, and openness to develop the digital twin of a temporary exhibition “The Other Renaissance” held in Bologna as part of the CHANGES project (Thematic Spoke 4: Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections) (RQ1). The project focused on the digitisation of hundreds of complex artefacts, necessitating the development and implementation of a thorough methodology. This paper presents our approach, using the Teriaca Vase as a case study. The Vase, an elaborately decorated container historically used in apothecaries to store the medicinal antidote theriaca, was selected from the exhibition to illustrate the application of our methodology. Our framework incorporates a paradata-based approach (Apollonio and Giovannini 2015), providing a detailed example of its practical implementation. This method aims to enhance 3D object reconstructions by increasing their informational complexity, integrating metadata that conveys the certainty and quality of the data alongside geometric and texture details (RQ2).

Methods and Materials

Digitisation is inherently imperfect due to technological and data collection limitations, resulting in gaps or inaccuracies. In our specific case, the high number of cultural heritage objects (CHOs) to digitise (301), their variety in terms of shapes, surfaces, and scales and the constraints of the exhibition’s limited timeframe and physical space were the main challenges to face. Addressing the issues due to these conditions involved a combination of automated processes and manual interventions, introducing some subjectivity and authorial actions. In this context, our research output provides a systematic taxonomy for data transparency, prioritising the preservation of three distinct versions of each 3D model derived from the raw acquisition data (RAW):

1. Processed Raw Data (RAWp): the first output from photogrammetry or scanning software for data processing, without interpolation or geometric corrections;

2. Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHO): a complete model after resolved geometry issues, gap filling, and interpolation during the 3D modelling phase using computer graphics software;
3. Optimised Digital Cultural Heritage Object (DCHOO): obtained during the optimisation phase to generate a further performant 3D model version designed for real-time interaction on web-based platforms (ATON framework was adopted).

Each stage in the pipeline, from acquisition to web-based publication, was carefully documented to ensure transparency and reproducibility (Barzaghi et al., 2024). Storing all derivative versions (RAWp, DCHO, and DCHOO) allows for direct comparison, offering a clear record of the authorial decisions and interventions made during the modelling process. The authorial aspect of reconstruction echoes the challenges of integrating missing portions of artefacts into virtual archaeological models, highlighting a shared methodology that can be adapted across domains to enhance reliability and applicability in diverse contexts. The developed pipeline achieved a level of photorealism consistent with the aim of dissemination and valorising cultural heritage. Starting from this premise, we propose a methodology to enhance data transparency further, making it suitable for documentation purposes as well.

Applying the process to the Teriaca (Figure 1) allowed for the creation of a lightweight and efficient 3D asset optimised for Web3D platforms. Polygon count was significantly reduced (from millions to thousands) while maintaining high local control over accuracy and topology. The subsequent UV mapping allowed for generating clear and readable 2D maps through baking. These maps aided in the controlled integration of missing parts in textures and geometry.

Both integrations have been stored and documented via a false-colour map associated with the same UV set so that it has been possible to subsequently deploy it as an alternative visualisation mode on the published asset. The colour map has been obtained by baking a vertex colour map associated with portions that have been filled during the mesh healing and repairing phase, and then enhanced during the integration of the same gaps in the textures, along with portions that were altered by low sampling in the texture projection during the digitisation of raw data.

Figure 1: rendering of the Teriaca Vase - artefact preserved by the Museo Civico Archeologico of Bologna.

Results

The digital twin pipeline was designed to produce outputs that meet the photorealistic requirements of a project with dissemination purposes. Efforts were made to utilise open formats and software at every step of the workflow aligning with FAIR principles. For the long-term preservation of 3D data, the team selected Zenodo as a temporary repository, given its adherence to Open Science principles.

The published digitised Teriaca DCHOO combines perceptual realism with low memory usage and quick Web3D loading, thanks to the optimisation of the geometry. It includes clear paradata to indicate integrated sections, enabling both casual users and specialists to explore the item and assess it before requesting raw data or the physical object for detailed study.

Discussion and conclusions

The proposed pipeline was tested for creating the Aldrovandi digital twin in the context of the CHANGES project. Paradata methodology will be further tested for future case studies within the same project. This approach may assess the integration of gaps for an extended ontology incorporating signed distances between the RAW and DCHOO meshes or other data visualised via false colour maps. Advanced acquisition techniques, (e.g., Gaussian splatting) will be explored to enhance the process further.

Bibliography

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